

Revisiting aerosol–cloud interactions from weekly cycles

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Key Points:

- The analysis of weekly cycles reveals a reduced sensitivity of cloud droplet number concentration to aerosol at larger aerosol loading.
- The strong weekly cycle in cloud cover is mainly a result of natural variability rather than being attributed to aerosol effects.
- Weekly cycles offer a useful pathway to investigating the Twomey effect, but are not as effective for detecting cloud adjustments.

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13 Abstract

14 Weekly cycles (WCs) in cloud properties have been reported and linked to aerosol
 15 effects. Yet the extent to which human activities contribute to their occurrence remains
 16 unclear. Here, we revisit aerosol–cloud interactions from the WCs over central Europe
 17 using long-term satellite and reanalysis data. Significant WCs in aerosol and cloud droplet
 18 number concentration (N_d) are detected with minima/maxima on Monday/Friday, in-
 19 dicating a clear signal of the Twomey effect. Notably, N_d -to-aerosol sensitivity from WCs
 20 is found to decrease at larger aerosol concentrations, confirming the nonlinear behavior
 21 of the aerosol– N_d relation (in log–log space) reported previously, but from a distinct per-
 22 spective. Nevertheless, no discernible WCs in liquid water path are found. The pronounced
 23 WCs in cloud cover are demonstrated to be driven by natural variability. Our results in-
 24 dicate that the WCs offer a useful pathway for investigating the Twomey effect, but are
 25 not as effective for detecting cloud adjustments.

26 Plain Language Summary

27 Aerosol–cloud interactions are the largest uncertainty in the anthropogenic forc-
 28 ing of climate. Specifically, an increase in aerosols increases cloud droplet number con-
 29 centration (the Twomey effect), which further changes liquid water path and cloud cover
 30 (cloud adjustments), ultimately alters radiations. Weekly cycles would be a useful tool
 31 for such study, assuming no seven-day periodicity in meteorological dynamics. In this
 32 study, we revisit aerosol–cloud interactions from weekly cycles using long-term satellite
 33 observations and reanalysis data. The analysis is restricted to central Europe – a region
 34 with strong weekly cycles in anthropogenic emissions. We find significant weekly cycles
 35 in aerosol and cloud droplet number concentration with minima/maxima on Monday/Friday.
 36 Importantly, the sensitivity of cloud droplet number concentration to aerosol is found
 37 to decrease in polluted conditions, confirming the behavior of the nonlinear cloud response
 38 to aerosol as reported previously. It is demonstrated that the weekly cycle in liquid wa-
 39 ter path is negligible; though a pronounced cycle in cloud cover detected, it is predom-
 40 inately caused by natural variability. Hence, caution is warranted when attributing ob-
 41 served weekly cycle in cloud cover to aerosol effects. Conclusively, weekly cycles are use-
 42 ful for detecting the Twomey effect but less effective for cloud adjustments.

43 1 Introduction

44 Human activity has led to an increase in atmospheric aerosols, in turn increasing
 45 the supply of cloud condensation nuclei (CCN). This will generate a cloud that consists
 46 of more but smaller droplets for a fixed liquid water content (the Twomey effect; Twomey,
 47 1974). The reduced droplet size can further change cloud cover and liquid water path
 48 (LWP) by altering precipitation (Albrecht, 1989) and evaporation processes (Ackerman
 49 et al., 2004), known as cloud adjustments. Despite decades of research, aerosol–cloud in-
 50 teractions (ACI) stubbornly remain the largest uncertainty in the anthropogenic forc-
 51 ing of climate (Forster et al., 2021).

52 For estimating ACI from observations, the most commonly used approach is to cor-
 53 relate aerosol–cloud quantities through spatio-temporal variability (Quaas et al., 2008).
 54 However, inferring causality from correlations is challenging (Gryspeerd et al., 2019; Mc-
 55 Coy et al., 2020), particularly when other confounders, such as meteorological variabil-
 56 ity and satellite retrieval errors play a role (Rosenfeld et al., 2023). In this regard, op-
 57 portunist experiments (volcanic eruptions, ship tracks, industrial sources, long-term
 58 trends, weekly cycles, etc.) that are assumed to perturb aerosols in a nearly unchanged
 59 meteorological background (Christensen et al., 2022), would provide additional insights
 60 into the ACI quantification.

61 Among these, weekly cycles (hereafter referred to as WCs) were mostly employed
 62 to investigate anthropogenic effects on air pollution (Xia et al., 2008; Georgoulias & Kour-
 63 tidis, 2011), and further to identify aerosol effects on temperature and precipitation (Sanchez-
 64 Lorenzo et al., 2012, and references therein). Though there were attempts on cloud cover,
 65 most investigations focused on local scale using surface observations (Bäumer & Vogel,
 66 2007; Sanchez-Lorenzo et al., 2008; Stjern, 2011; Wang et al., 2012). Quaas et al. (2009)
 67 took an initial step toward satellite-observed WCs in cloud microphysical properties over
 68 Europe, finding a distinct WC in cloud droplet number concentrations (N_d), but rather
 69 weak signals in cloud cover and LWP. In contrast, a follow-up study reported a strong
 70 WC in cloud cover over similar region, and interpreted it as an indirect effect (Georgou-
 71 lias et al., 2015). However, in either case, possible natural variability was not eliminated,
 72 which is particular important as cloud cover is very susceptible to the meteorological co-
 73 variability (Mauger & Norris, 2007). Although no meteorological mechanism is supposed
 74 to have a seven-day periodicity, the spurious WCs in temperature were found (Quaas et
 75 al., 2009; Kim & Roh, 2010), highlighting the importance of isolating anthropogenic con-
 76 tributions.

77 Additionally, it was reported that the aerosol– N_d relationship in log–log space is
 78 nonlinear (Gryspeerd et al., 2017) – a reduced N_d sensitivity ($\beta_{N_d} = \frac{d \ln N_d}{d \ln \alpha}$, where
 79 α is a proxy for CCN concentration) with aerosol under medium-to-polluted conditions,
 80 conflicting with the commonly linear assumption, which strongly affects the estimates
 81 of ACI forcing (Jia & Quaas, 2023). Note that the relations in Jia & Quaas (2023) were
 82 constructed based on aerosol–cloud variabilities in daily and decadal scales. To check the
 83 robustness of the finding, it is thus useful to look at the $\ln \alpha$ – $\ln N_d$ relationship from a
 84 different angle. Specificity, does β_{N_d} derived from WCs rely on aerosol backgrounds?

85 To tackle the aforementioned issues, we revisit the ACI from satellite-observed WCs,
 86 with following updates over previous investigations: 1) larger data volume gathered from
 87 a longer study period (2001–2019) to reduce the statistical uncertainty; 2) more reliable
 88 retrievals of aerosol and N_d ; 3) insights into the nonlinearity of the $\ln \alpha$ – $\ln N_d$; 4) sep-
 89 aration of anthropogenic and natural contributions to the observed WCs in cloud cover.
 90 The meaningful detection of WCs in cloud properties is possible only when aerosol is suf-
 91 ficiently perturbed. Therefore, this study is restricted to central Europe, where a robust
 92 and uniform weekly pattern in aerosol is observed across the entire area compared to spa-
 93 tially spread signals in other industrial regions (Supplemental Figure 1).

94 2 Data and Methods

95 2.1 Data

96 The main aerosol quantity in this study is aerosol optical depth (AOD) from the
 97 MODIS Terra & Aqua Collection 6.1 Level-3 daily products (Levy et al., 2013). It has
 98 been shown that aerosol index (AI) is better suited for investigating ACI than AOD (Gryspeerd
 99 et al., 2017; Hasekamp et al., 2019); however, MODIS aerosol size parameters are not
 100 quantitatively reliable over land. Therefore, the polarimetric retrievals (AOD and AI)
 101 from the POL arization and Directionality of Earth’s Reflectance-3 (POLDER-3), which
 102 have better quantitative skills in aerosol size over land (Hasekamp et al., 2011, 2023),
 103 are utilized as supplementary dataset, albeit with less available data compared to MODIS.

104 Total cloud cover (TCC), liquid cloud cover (LiqCC), LWP and cloud droplet ef-
 105 fective radius (CER) are directly from MODIS Terra & Aqua Collection 6.1 Level-3 daily
 106 products (Platnick et al., 2017). LiqCC is defined as TCC with ice cloud fraction < 0.005 .
 107 The results do not change significantly while choosing different thresholds from 0 to 0.05
 108 (Supplemental Figure 2). N_d is obtained from a MODIS-based dataset (Gryspeerd et
 109 al., 2022a) that provides N_d Level-3 products based on different sampling strategies. Con-
 110 sidering the balance of accuracy and data coverage (Gryspeerd et al., 2022b), we focus

111 on the N_d from the strategy of Grosvenor et al. (2018) while also looking into the po-
 112 tential impact of different sampling strategies (Quaas et al., 2006; Bennartz & Rausch,
 113 2017; Grosvenor et al., 2018; Zhu et al., 2018). Note that microphysical properties are
 114 restricted to liquid water clouds. Also, the TCC–cloud top pressure (CTP) joint histogram
 115 is used to derive MODIS low cloud cover (LCC; see section 2.2).

The short-wave planetary albedo for all-sky (A_{all}) and clear-sky (A_{clr}) conditions are from the Clouds and the Earth’s Radiant Energy System (CERES) SSF1deg Edition-4 Level-3 daily product (Wielicki et al., 1996). Cloud albedo (A_{clid}) is computed from A_{all} and A_{clr} according to Eq.1, where A_{clid} represents the cloud albedo per unit cloud cover.

$$A_{\text{all}} = \text{LiqCCA}_{\text{clid}} + (1 - \text{LiqCC})A_{\text{clr}} \quad (1)$$

116 The Global Precipitation Climatology Project data (Huffman et al., 2023) is used
 117 to distinguish precipitation state. Meteorological variables, including potential temper-
 118 ature (θ), relative humidity (RH) are taken from the European Centre for Medium-Range
 119 Weather Forecasts ERA5 reanalysis data (Hersbach et al., 2020). Lower tropospheric sta-
 120 bility (LTS) is calculated as the difference between θ_{700hPa} and $\theta_{1000hPa}$ (Klein & Hart-
 121 mann, 1993). Notably, in the ERA5, clouds are calculated using a parameterization based
 122 on the thermodynamic state of the atmosphere, and thus do not interact with aerosol
 123 (Hersbach et al., 2020). This implies that the WCs from ERA5 are mostly driven by nat-
 124 ural variability. Therefore, ERA5 cloud cover will be compared with the MODIS one to
 125 isolate the anthropogenic and natural contributions. Since ERA5 does not provide liq-
 126 uid cloud cover, ERA5 TCC (TCC_{ERA5}) and LCC (LCC_{ERA5}) will be analyzed, with
 127 the latter being more relevant to liquid-phase clouds.

128 The daily $1^\circ \times 1^\circ$ gridded data spanning the years 2001–2019 are employed to achieve
 129 statistically significant results through a substantial sample size. Note that POLDER
 130 data span from 2006 to 2009. The hourly ERA5 quantities are matched to 10:30 (13:30)
 131 local solar time to approximate the overpass time of the Terra (Aqua) satellite.

132 2.2 Derivation of MODIS low cloud cover

133 As the MODIS operational products do not directly provide LCC to be compared
 134 with ERA5, here we derive the MODIS LCC using two independent methods.

ERA5 has been demonstrated to reasonably capture the vertical structure of cloud layers (Zhao et al., 2023), with deviations in high, medium and low cloud covers from observations all remaining within 0.06 (Tan et al., 2022). Thus, LCC can be inferred by multiplying TCC by the ratio of LCC_{ERA5} to TCC_{ERA5} , with ‘ r ’ in subscript denoting the LCC derived by this ‘ratio’ method.

$$\text{LCC}_r = \frac{\text{LCC}_{\text{ERA5}}}{\text{TCC}_{\text{ERA5}}} \text{TCC} \quad (2)$$

135 Additionally, we calculate LCC based on the MODIS TCC-CTP joint histogram with-
 136 out relying on model.

$$\text{LCC}_p = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^{12} \sum_{j=8}^{10} n(i, j) \text{TCC}(i) + p \sum_{i=1}^{12} \sum_{j=1}^7 n(i, j) \text{TCC}(i)}{N_{\text{tot}}}, \quad p \in [0, 0.2, 0.5] \quad (3)$$

137 where $n(i, j)$ is the histogram of the i -th bin of TCC and the j -th bin of CTP. The MODIS
 138 TCC–CTP joint histogram has 12 TCC bins and 10 CTP bins. Consistent with the def-
 139 inition in ERA5, a low cloud here is assumed as the cloud with CTP larger than 800 hPa
 140 ($j \geq 8$). N_{tot} is total number of Level-2 observations within each Level-3 grid box. p
 141 is the assumed percentage of mid-to-high clouds with the presence of low clouds beneath

142 them, which is used as the subscript of LCC_p to distinguish the LCC derived from vary-
 143 ing assumptions of p .

144 The derived LCC_r and $LCC_{0.5}$ show good agreements with LCC_{ERA5} in terms of
 145 both magnitude and spatial pattern, with determination coefficients of 0.97 and 0.71 ([Sup-](#)
 146 [plemental Figure 3](#)); $LCC_{0.2}$ and LCC_0 show similar patterns as LCC_{ERA5} , but with un-
 147 derestimated values. As such, LCC_r and $LCC_{0.5}$ will be used in the main text.

148 3 Results

149 To quantify the WC, the range of WC is defined as the peak-to-trough difference
 150 in both absolute and relative terms. The Kruskal-Wallis test is used to determine the
 151 significance of WC. [Table S1](#) summarizes the WC range, the occurrence of peak/trough
 152 day and the Kruskal-Wallis significance for each aerosol and cloud quantity. As Terra
 153 and Aqua have similar variations, only values for Aqua are quoted in the main text.

154 3.1 Implications for the Twomey effect

155 3.1.1 Weekly cycles in aerosol and N_d

156 As a result of reduced emissions on weekends compared to weekdays, a clear WC
 157 in AOD is present with minima on Monday and maxima on Friday, with the WC range
 158 being 0.02 (8.97%) ([Figure 1a](#)). A co-incident WC is seen in N_d with the range of 7.1 cm^{-3}
 159 (3.77%) ([Figure 1b](#)). CER shows a weak weekly variation, owing to the changing LWP
 160 ([Supplemental Figure 5](#)). The Kruskal-Wallis test indicates significant Friday-to-Monday
 161 differences in AOD and N_d . Despite not showing identical day-to-day variations, the weekly
 162 patterns of AOD and N_d still exhibit a strong correlation, with a coefficient (R) of 0.9.
 163 Owing to the stronger WCs in anthropogenic emissions over central Europe, the ampli-
 164 tudes are double compared to those derived for the entire European continent – approx-
 165 imately 5% for AOD and 2% for N_d (Quaas et al., 2009; Christensen et al., 2022). It
 166 is interesting that both can be translated into nearly the same β_{N_d} ($\frac{d \ln N_d}{d \ln AOD}$) of ~ 0.4 ,
 167 falling within the plausible range of 0.3–0.8 suggested by Bellouin et al. (2020), albeit
 168 towards its lower end.

169 However, in the conventional correlation approach, the satellite-derived β_{N_d} over
 170 land was often reported as a negative value (Grandey & Stier, 2010; Gryspeerdt & Stier,
 171 2012; Ma et al., 2018), which was attributed to co-varied retrieval errors in aerosol and
 172 N_d (Jia et al., 2019, 2022) and precipitation (Yang et al., 2021). To investigate if retrieval
 173 biases also play a role in the WCs approach, we compare different aerosol and N_d prod-
 174 ucts. It is found that the ranges of WCs nearly remain the same when applying differ-
 175 ent aerosol retrieval algorithms and N_d sampling strategies ([Supplemental Figure 6&7](#));
 176 thereby pointing to similar β_{N_d} . It is noted that AOD and AI show the same WCs in
 177 the POLDER polarimetric measurements that have proficient quantitative skills in aerosol
 178 size ([Supplemental Figure 3](#)). These results suggest that, in comparison to the conven-
 179 tional correlation approach, the β_{N_d} derived by the WCs approach are considerably less
 180 sensitive to the retrieval biases and the choice of CCN proxy. Furthermore, the WCs demon-
 181 strate the ability to predict the long-term change in N_d , thus the Twomey effect. From
 182 2002 to 2019, AOD over central Europe decreases by 41% (from 0.28 to 0.2), and the
 183 predicted N_d reduction is 17%, in close agreement with its actual decline 19%. While
 184 the predicted and observed trends are slight different, their uncertainty ranges largely
 185 overlap ([Supplemental Figure 8](#)).

186 Moreover, the range of WC in AOD in the non-precipitating case is larger than that
 187 in the precipitating case ([Figure 1c](#)), possibly due to the aerosol scavenging by precip-
 188 itation veiling the real variability of AOD. In contrast, a stronger N_d range is observed
 189 in the precipitating case ([Figure 1d](#)), possibly due to a more intensive N_d sink by pre-

190 precipitation on the cleaner weekends. The amplified N_d WC in the precipitating case indirectly supports the hypothesis of suppressed liquid-phase precipitation by aerosols (Albrecht, 1989) over land.
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Figure 1. Weekly cycles in AOD and N_d and the implied β_{N_d} . **a–b**, Weekly cycles obtained from Terra (gray) and Aqua (black) during the entire period (2001–2019). **c–d**, Weekly cycles for all (black), non-precipitating (yellow) and precipitating (light blue) cases during 2001–2019. **e–f**, Weekly cycles during polluted (red; 2002–2010) and clean (blue; 2011–2019) periods. **g**, Variations in AOD (gray bars) and β_{N_d} (crosses) over time. Data volumes (N) used for calculating weekly cycles are presented in their respective colors. **c–g** are based on Aqua observations. Similar results from Terra are shown in [Supplemental Figure 4](#). Note that β_{N_d} is calculated by dividing the WC range in N_d by that in AOD, thus the uncertainty range as in the correlation approach is not given here. All weekly cycles shown in this study are in relative terms, i.e., percent deviation from mean value [%], unless otherwise noted.

3.1.2 Dependence of β_{N_d} on aerosol loading

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194 Given the monotonic decline in anthropogenic emissions over Europe, the first and
 195 second halves of past two decades are selected to represent relatively polluted (2002–2010)
 196 and clean (2011–2019) scenarios. [Figure 1e,f](#) illustrates that clear WCs in AOD and N_d
 197 exist in both periods i.e., maxima on Friday and minima on Monday/Sunday. As AOD
 198 decreases, we see a slight reduction in AOD range (from 10.3% to 9.77%; [Figure 1e](#)) but
 199 a sharp increase in N_d range (from 2.84% to 4.65%; [Figure 1f](#)). This is consequently
 200 translated into an increase in β_{N_d} from 0.28 to 0.48 with aerosol decreasing ([Figure 1g](#)).

201 Similar behaviours also appear in Terra-based results with a β_{N_d} increase of 0.23 to 0.58
 202 (Supplemental Figure 4). Again, no clear differences in CER WCs are detected between
 203 two periods (Supplemental Figure 5). In addition to the approaches based on aerosol-
 204 cloud variabilities on daily and decadal scales in Jia & Quaas (2023), the WCs here pro-
 205 vide a separate line of evidence for the nonlinearity of the $\ln \alpha$ - $\ln N_d$ relationship. That
 206 is, with the same (even smaller) aerosol perturbation, the response of N_d tends to be more
 207 pronounced in a clean condition; in other words, the ACI-induced cooling will diminish
 208 more rapidly with efforts to mitigate air pollution.

209 3.2 Implications for rapid adjustments of LWP and cloud cover

210 3.2.1 Weekly cycles in LWP and cloud cover

211 The variations in LWP do not follow the 7-day periodicity in anthropogenic emis-
 212 sions (Figure 2c,f), and no significant Fri-to-Mon differences are observed according to
 213 the Kruskal-Wallis test. The undetectable WCs agree with other assessments based on
 214 weekly cycles (Quaas et al., 2009), long-term trends (Quaas et al., 2022), industrial sources
 215 (Toll et al., 2019) and volcanic eruptions (Malavelle et al., 2017; Chen et al., 2022). De-
 216 spite more pronounced LWP responses observed in ship tracks (Gryspeerd et al., 2021;
 217 Manshausen et al., 2022, 2023), this effect is likely overestimated (Glassmeier et al., 2021).
 218 Unlike the invisible WCs in TCC reported by Quaas et al. (2009), clearer WCs in TCC
 219 and LiqCC are detected here (Figure 2a,b), with the ranges of 0.01 (1.61 %) and 0.03
 220 (4.56 %), respectively. According to current understanding from observations, the sensi-
 221 tivity of cloud-cover to N_d ($\beta_C = \frac{d \ln \text{LiqCC}}{d \ln N_d}$) would be up to ~ 0.4 (Gryspeerd et al.,
 222 2016; Rosenfeld et al., 2019; Chen et al., 2022; Quaas et al., 2022). The WCs, however,
 223 yield an unexpectedly high β_C of 1.21 for liquid clouds. On the other hand, the strong
 224 WCs in TCC and LiqCC stem from non-precipitating clouds (Figure 2d,e). This is again
 225 somewhat counter-intuitive, as the stronger WCs should appear in all and precipitating
 226 cases because the cloud-cover adjustment is achieved via modifying precipitation. Even
 227 though clearly consistent WCs in TCC and LiqCC are detected, no conclusion regard-
 228 ing aerosol effects can be drawn without distangling anthropogenic effects from others.

Figure 2. Same as Figure 1 but for TCC, LiqCC and LWP. Similar results from Terra are shown in Supplemental Figure 9.

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3.2.2 Strong weekly cycle in cloud cover: anthropogenic or natural?

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To separate the anthropogenic and natural contributions, we contrast the cloud cover from MODIS and ERA5 (Figure 3), with the latter being considered as a proxy for non-anthropogenic variability (as outlined in the section 2).

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Interestingly, TCC_{ERA5} exhibits a very similar weekly pattern as MODIS TCC (Figure 3a,b), which is statistically significant by the Kruskal-Wallis test ($p \leq 0.001$). Also, their WCs ranges are nearly identical with the values of 0.01 (1.41 %) for TCC_{ERA5} and 0.01 (1.61 %) for MODIS TCC. Consequently, after extracting the natural variability, the WCs in TCC clearly disappear (Figure 3c), indicating no observable anthropogenic effects on the WCs in TCC. Similar behaviours are also seen in the WCs in LCC, regardless of the specific method employed to derive the MODIS LCC (Figure 3d-i). In the purely MODIS-based method (Eq 3), a p value of 0.5 is selected for the best agreement in LCC spatial distributions between MODIS and ERA5 as clarified in the Method section; here, we further demonstrate in Supplemental Figure 10 that the WCs in LCC are independent on the choice of p , confirming the robustness of the analysis.

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It should be noted that although cloud cover is not directly assimilated in ERA5, temperature and RH are indeed assimilated. This, in turn, implies that any aerosol-induced weekly signal of LTS and RH might indirectly affect ERA5 modeled cloud cover. Supplemental Figure 11 shows that the weekday-weekend difference is only evinced in LTS, which is governed by the variability of θ_{700hPa} . Although absorbing aerosols can increase LTS (Ding et al., 2016), local-emitted ones are mostly within the boundary layer (Guo et al., 2021, ~ 1 km over Europe), which is unlikely to change θ_{700hPa} . Therefore, any aerosol-radiation feedback is not likely to impose a WC signal to the model via assimilation.

Figure 3. Comparison of weekly cycles in cloud cover from ERA5 and MODIS. **a–c**, Total cloud cover from ERA5 (TCC_{ERA5} ; **a**) and MODIS (TCC; **b**), along with their difference ($TCC - TCC_{ERA5}$; **c**). **d–f**, Low cloud cover from ERA5 (LCC_{ERA5} ; **d**) and MODIS TCC–CTP joint histogram with p of 0.5 ($LCC_{0.5}$; **e**), along with their difference ($LCC_{0.5} - LCC_{ERA5}$; **f**). **g–i**, Same as **d–f** but MODIS LCC calculated based on TCC and low-to-total cloud cover ratio from ERA5 (LCC_r). The hourly ERA5 quantities at 10:30 & 13:30 local solar time are selected to approximate the overpass time of Terra & Aqua satellites. Data volumes (N) are also shown.

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3.3 Radiation response

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Quaas et al. (2009) did not find robust WCs in radiation and attributed it to insufficient data volume collected over ~ 8 years. With 19-year data here, we show smoothly discernible WCs in A_{all} (minima on Monday and maxima on Friday) with the range of 0.01 (1.31 %) (Figure 4a), which means a change in solar radiation of $\sim 3.4 \text{ W m}^{-2}$ (considering the incoming solar radiation of 341.2 W m^{-2}). This value is already a factor of three larger than the multi-model mean aerosol forcing ($\sim -1.2 \text{ W m}^{-2}$ over 1850–2014) over central Europe (Szopa et al., 2021). We should note that the aerosol perturbation made on a weekly scale ($\sim 10\%$) is much smaller than the anthropogenic perturbation since pre-industrial times (McCoy et al., 2017). Therefore, if the actual anthropogenic aerosol perturbation was applied to the weekly results here, the resulting radiation change would far exceed the currently reported aerosol forcing. This confirms that the observed WCs in A_{all} are not fully anthropogenic-driven.

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Despite the strong N_d WCs, there are no clear WCs in A_{cld} (Figure 4b) mainly owing to the noisy LWP variations. A_{cld} exhibits a stronger correlation with LWP ($R=0.7$) than with N_d ($R=-0.1$). Similarly, there are no distinguishable WCs in A_{clr} despite the peak on Friday (Figure 4c). Unlike A_{cld} , the observed WCs in A_{all} appear to be driven by cloud cover ($R=0.9$). Since the WCs in A_{all} lead to a radiation change that apparently exceeds the upper bound of plausible aerosol forcing, the observed WCs in cloud cover are thus mainly explained by the natural variability.

Figure 4. Weekly cycles in the top-of-atmosphere albedo for Terra (gray) and Aqua (black). **a**, All-sky albedo (A_{all}). **b**, Cloud albedo (A_{cld}). **c**, Clear-sky albedo (A_{clr}). Data volumes (N) are shown.

4 Conclusions and Discussion

This study revisits the aerosol–cloud interactions via examining weekly cycles in aerosol, cloud and radiation over central Europe from long-term satellite observations in combination with reanalysis data.

We detected a clear signal of the Twomey effect from WCs. In responding to the weekly periodicity in anthropogenic emissions, consistent WCs are detected in AOD and N_d with minima/maxima on Monday/Friday. The amplitudes of WCs in AOD and N_d offer an alternative pathway to quantify β_{N_d} . Unlike the negative β_{N_d} obtained from the correlation approach, the WCs approach provides a plausible estimation of ~ 0.4 . Additionally, the WCs-based β_{N_d} was demonstrated to be less sensitive to the retrieval biases and the choice of CCN proxy than the conventional correlation approach. Furthermore, the difference in WCs-based β_{N_d} under polluted and clean periods reveals a decrease in β_{N_d} with aerosol loading. This supports the finding based on daily and decadal aerosol– N_d variabilities (Jia & Quaas, 2023): the $\ln \alpha$ – $\ln N_d$ relationship is not linear as commonly assumed in the observation-based β_{N_d} calculation. This confirms that a single $\ln \alpha$ – $\ln N_d$ slope is unable to properly link current N_d to its pre-industrial state; instead, the nonlinear fitting that considers the full variability of β_{N_d} , would be a promising alternative (Jia & Quaas, 2023).

Unlike the Twomey effect, cloud adjustments are undetectable through the WCs. There are no discernible WCs in LWP. As for cloud cover, despite the observed strong WCs in TCC and LCC, there are no WCs signal left after removing the ERA5 natural weekly variation. Note that we cannot completely reject the existence of residual anthropogenic contributions in ERA5, as the assimilations of real meteorological parameters might indirectly feed aerosol-induced weekly signal back to modelled cloud cover. This influence was, however, shown to be small. In addition to the MODIS–ERA5 contrast, there are extra lines of evidence supporting the conclusion that the observed WCs in cloud cover are not driven by anthropogenic effects. Firstly, the WCs in LiqCC result in an unrealistically high β_C of 1.2; secondly, the WCs in TCC and LiqCC are caused by non-precipitating cases, conflicting with the hypothesis that aerosol increases cloud cover via altering the precipitation (Albrecht, 1989). Moreover, the WCs in A_{all} dominated by cloud cover, are equivalent to a 3.4 W m^{-2} change in solar radiation, which is much larger than the plausible total aerosol forcing ($\sim 1.2 \text{ W m}^{-2}$) over Europe.

Our WCs results suggest a much weaker cloud-cover adjustment over a continental mid-latitude region compared to that over the global oceans (Rosenfeld et al., 2019; Forster et al., 2021; Chen et al., 2022; Wall et al., 2023; Yuan et al., 2023). However, no cloud adjustments detected here does not necessarily mean the effects are negligible. Caveats of WCs approach should be also noted. It is challenging to interpret a 7-day oscillation

309 to an aerosol-induced cycle. Thus, the WCs approach requires considerably larger vari-
 310 ability in aerosol than in metrological background, a condition that, however, is not al-
 311 ways met. Even for central Europe where the strongest aerosol WCs are observed, the
 312 resulting perturbation in N_d is only 4%, which is much lower than the perturbations yielded
 313 in other opportunistic experiments, e.g., larger than 100% for industrial tracks (Toll et
 314 al., 2019), 27% for volcanic eruptions (Chen et al., 2022), 20% for pollution trajecto-
 315 ries (Christensen et al., 2020) and 10~20% for long-term trends (Quaas et al., 2022; Jia
 316 & Quaas, 2023). Such weak N_d perturbation makes it very difficult to identify cloud ad-
 317 justments from natural variability.

318 Conclusively, to apply the WCs approach in ACI studies, it is crucial to ensure 1)
 319 sufficient perturbations in driving factors (e.g., aerosol for N_d , N_d for LWP and cloud
 320 cover), 2) the observed WCs being driving by anthropogenic activities, and 3) the de-
 321 rived cloud susceptibility within a reasonable range. Here, we show that the WCs ap-
 322 proach works well for N_d ; however, for LWP and cloud cover that are highly suscepti-
 323 ble to the metrological conditions, the WCs might not be a desirable approach. There-
 324 fore, no definitive conclusion can be drawn on whether the negligible aerosol-induced WCs
 325 in cloud cover signify a weak cloud adjustment or suggest the unsuitability of the ap-
 326 proach. Our results emphasize that caution must be exercised when interpreting the ob-
 327 served WCs in cloud cover as being caused by an aerosol effect.

328 5 Open Research

329 5.1 Data Availability Statement

330 The MODIS Level 3 products are available from the Atmosphere Archive and Dis-
 331 tribution System (LAADS) Distributed Active Archive Center (DAAC): [https://ladsweb.
 332 modaps.eosdis.nasa.gov/archive/allData/61/MYD08_D3/](https://ladsweb.modaps.eosdis.nasa.gov/archive/allData/61/MYD08_D3/) (Platnick et al., 2017a) and
 333 https://ladsweb.modaps.eosdis.nasa.gov/archive/allData/61/MOD08_D3/ (Platnick et
 334 al., 2017b). The POLDER-3/PARASOL polarimetric retrievals by the SRON RemoTAP
 335 algorithm are available from SRON at www.sron.nl/harpol (Hasekamp et al., 2023). The
 336 MODIS-based N_d dataset with different sampling strategies are available from the Cen-
 337 tre for Environmental Data Analysis at [https://doi.org/10.5285/864a46cc65054008857ee5bb
 338 772a2a2b](https://doi.org/10.5285/864a46cc65054008857ee5bb772a2a2b) (Gryspeerd et al., 2022a). The CERES SSF Level 3 products are obtained
 339 from the NASA Langley Research Center CERES ordering tool at [https://ceres.larc.nasa.gov/
 340 data/](https://ceres.larc.nasa.gov/data/) (CERES Science Team, 2023a,b). The Global Precipitation Climatology Project
 341 data are obtained from the NOAA National Centers for Environmental Information at
 342 [https://www.ncei.noaa.gov/data/global-precipitation-climatology-project-gpcp-daily/
 343 \(Adler et al., 2017\). The ERA5 reanalysis products are available at https://www.ecmwf
 344 .int/en/forecasts/dataset/ecmwf-reanalysis-v5](https://www.ncei.noaa.gov/data/global-precipitation-climatology-project-gpcp-daily/) (Hersbach et al., 2023).

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